

Using bench protocol platforms to improve compliance with systematic review guidance documents and reporting checklists: proof of concept~~A general-purpose protocol for facilitating standards compliance when planning systematic reviews~~

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Abstract

Context: A [significant](#) number of ~~conduct standards~~[guidance documents](#) and reporting checklists have been published to support researchers in planning, doing, and writing up scientifically rigorous systematic reviews (SRs). However, compliance [of researchers](#) with SR ~~conduct standards~~[guidance](#) and reporting checklists remains a significant challenge, [with the majority of published SRs lacking in one or more aspects of rigour of methods and transparency of reporting.](#)

Objective: ~~We hypothesise that compliance with conduct standards and checklists~~[To explore how bench protocol development platforms might be repurposed for improving compliance of SRs with conduct guidance and reporting checklists. how technical tools that support the planning and documentation of](#)

24 ~~primary research can be adapted for the purpose of improving author compliance with SR guidance and~~
25 ~~checklists.~~

26 ~~can be improved by reducing the amount of experience required for successfully using such standards~~
27 ~~and checklists in a research process.~~

28 **Methods**~~System design:~~ We developed a proof-of-concept technology stack based around a general-
29 purpose, guidance- and checklist-compliant SR protocol that was built in protocols.io. We used the
30 protocols.io platform to create an integrated research planning and data collection into a structured
31 process for planning guidance-compliant SRs, labelled the collected data, and u We used our own
32 custom code and the mustache templating language to automatically create from the labelled data
33 checklist-compliant first-draft SR protocol documents in Microsoft Word.

34 ~~To set the initial groundwork for testing this hypothesis, we developed a proof-of-concept general-purpose~~
35 ~~SR protocol using the protocols.io platform, modified the output to consist of labelled data, and developed~~
36 ~~code and a template for automated creation of a draft protocol manuscript from the labelled data.~~

37 **Discussion:** Creating the operational process for SR protocol planning and the technology stack for
38 automated documentation allowed us to develop our theoretical understanding of how such a system may
39 improve compliance with research conduct and reporting standards. This includes the potential value of
40 algorithmic rather than heuristic approaches to conducting and reporting research studies, positioning of
41 labelled data rather than a study manuscript as the primary product of the research process, and viewing
42 the process of developing research standards as being analogous to development of open software.

43 ~~Finally~~Our study also allowed us to ,we identifiedidentify a number of specific and general technological
44 issues in our technology stack that would~~that will~~ need to be addressed to enable further development
45 and testing of our proposed approach. These include limitations in templating language, especially when
46 working in Microsoft Word, and the need for more data labelling and export formats from protocols.io.

47

48 **Introduction**

49 A number of conduct ~~standards-guidelines~~ and reporting checklists have been published to
 50 support researchers in planning, doing, and writing up scientifically rigorous systematic reviews
 51 (SRs). However, compliance with SR conduct ~~standards-guidelines~~ and reporting checklists
 52 appears to be a significant challenge for researchers, with consistent evidence of shortcomings
 53 in the methodological rigour and comprehensiveness of documentation of SRs from a range of
 54 research fields including healthcare (Page *et al.*, 2016; Gao *et al.*, 2019), environmental science
 55 (Pullin *et al.*, 2022), socioeconomics (Wang *et al.*, 2021), and human environmental health
 56 (Menon, Struijs and Whaley, 2022). This is potentially a significant source of research waste or
 57 even societal harm, with significant resources being used to conduct SRs that may be
 58 redundant, present inaccurate findings, or both (Ioannidis, 2016).

59 Conduct ~~standards-guidelines specify~~ specify sets of requirements that what a SR ought to
 60 do, needs to meet in order to attain a certain level of scientific quality. ~~The intent is to provide~~
 61 ~~researchers with a list of criteria that, if met, should ensure a SR has,~~ with “quality” generally
 62 understood in terms of some desired combination of usefulness, credibility (e.g. by reducing
 63 bias), and transparency (Whaley, Aiassa, *et al.*, 2020). ~~We believe one important obstacle to~~
 64 ~~compliance with conduct standards is their complexity, which creates a high experience~~
 65 ~~requirement on the part of researchers for their successful use.~~ SR ~~standards-guidelines~~ tend to
 66 be lengthy and complex., ~~with~~ ~~†~~ The Institute of Medicine guidance on SRs ~~consisting~~ consists of
 67 82 performance elements and extensive narrative text (Institute of Medicine, 2011), ~~†~~. ~~The~~
 68 Cochrane MECIR standard consists of over 75 performance elements accompanied by a
 69 handbook of over 700 pages (Cochrane, 2019; Higgins, JPT *et al.*, 2019), ~~and~~ ~~†~~ The COSTER
 70 recommendations for SRs of environmental health research of consists of 70 elements (Whaley,
 71 Aiassa, *et al.*, 2020). ~~Such~~ ~~†~~ length and complexity of guidance is probably unavoidable when
 72 formalising the necessary components of a research process that is in itself lengthy and
 73 complex. ~~Nonetheless, such complexity presents; however, it presents~~ a considerable
 74 organisational challenge for authors seeking to ~~successfully~~ comply with ~~each and every~~
 75 ~~component of a standard~~ SR guideline. This challenge requires a significant level of experience
 76 to overcome, to understand specialist vocabulary used in guidance documents and the often
 77 complex concepts that terms in the vocabulary may signify, and the unmentioned actions and
 78 practices (relating to e.g. resourcing, management, training, and documentation) that need to be
 79 undertaken to comply with an superficially simple recommendation or requirement. Nuance and
 80 cultural knowledge of this type is challenging, if not impossible, for ~~which the~~ guidance

81 ~~document itself cannot of finite length to provide, or at least for a user of guidance to~~
82 ~~successfully internalise provide. To put it another way: there is a fundamental difference~~
83 ~~between knowing what to do (the recommendations presented in a guidance document) and~~
84 ~~knowing how to do it successfully (the resourcing, planning, training, etc. that are not described~~
85 ~~in the guidance but are necessary to meet the recommendations in the guidance).~~

86 Reporting checklists are intended to support authors in providing enough information about
87 what they did and found in the course of conducting a SR that a reader can follow their methods
88 and appraise the credibility of their results (Moher *et al.*, 2014). As for conduct
89 ~~standards guidelines~~, we believe there is a high experience requirement for their successful use.
90 One aspect of this experience requirement is the necessity for users and writers of a checklist to
91 share the same understanding of how terms describing checklist items map onto the processes
92 of a systematic review. Ways in which ~~this we have observed this breaking can break~~ down in a
93 PRISMA report (Page *et al.*, 2021), for example, include the misidentification of risk of bias with
94 other study appraisal methods, and the conflation of the Population-Exposure-Comparator-
95 Outcome (PECO) statement for describing the objectives of a SR with PECO-derived eligibility
96 criteria ~~foref~~ a SR (Menon, Struijs and Whaley, 2022). Further complicating things, ~~each item in~~
97 ~~a reporting checklist implies~~ a certain set of recommended practices that may not be explicit
98 and might not have been followed by the research team using the checklist ~~(for example,~~
99 ~~reporting a valid search may, in terms of implied guidance, require engaging with an information~~
100 ~~specialist).~~

101 Proficiency in the technical jargon and implied practices in systematic review requires a
102 potentially lengthy period of acculturation in relevant, competent communities of practice. Seen
103 in those terms, successful use of ~~guidance and~~ checklists ~~like MECIR and PRISMA~~ could be as
104 much an indicator of successful acculturation ~~to a systematic review community (or specifically,~~
105 ~~MECIR- or PRISMA-centric subcommunities)~~ as they are a facilitator of writing up rigorous SR
106 manuscripts.

107 ~~We speculate that the experience requirement for successful compliance with guidance and~~
108 ~~checklists can could be lowered, if the content of guidance and checklists can be reconfigured as~~
109 ~~in the following way... We hypothesise that the experience requirement for successful use of~~
110 ~~standards and checklists may be lowered by:~~ (1) ~~by~~ interpreting ~~on behalf of a user~~ the
111 recommendations of a conduct standard into a sequence of ~~task-list style~~ operational steps that
112 can be followed by a research team; and (2) ~~by enabling the user to~~ recording what is done in

113 each operational step in such a way that [the](#) data can later be automatically ~~retrieved~~[used](#) for a
114 given reporting task. ~~To provide a foundation for testing this hypothesis and exploring the~~
115 ~~technical requirements of such a system, we~~

116 [A recent technological innovation that could allow for this reduction in experience](#)
117 [requirement is provided by bench protocol platforms such as protocols.io \(Teytelman et al.](#)
118 [2016\), that facilitate “detailing, sharing, and discussing molecular and computational protocols”.](#)
119 [Bench protocol platforms have not been directly designed for automating compliance with](#)
120 [complex research guidance and reporting checklists. However, they have several features](#)
121 [including detailed recording of operational procedures, data capture when following those](#)
122 [procedures, and data export functions that allow captured data to be reused, that suggest they](#)
123 [could be appropriated for this purpose.](#)

124 [To better understand how bench protocol tools can be repurposed for complex research](#)
125 [design and documentation tasks, ~~We therefore~~](#) set out to build a [proof-of-concept](#) general-
126 purpose operational template for planning and reporting a human environmental health SR. The
127 template is designed to have the following features:

- 128 1. Be an explicit, step-by-step sequence of operational procedures for developing and
129 documenting a human environmental health SR protocol ([“operational procedure”](#));
- 130 2. [A mapping of](#)~~Map~~ how each step in the template’s operational procedure translates into
131 compliance with a selected set of conduct standards and reporting checklists
132 ([“compliance mapping”](#));
- 133 3. [Have as output structured, labelled data](#)~~Labelling of the steps and data outputs of the~~
134 [general protocol](#), to render machine-readable the operational procedures and [data](#)
135 ~~outputs~~ [data of the protocol](#) ([“data labelling”](#));
- 136 4. ~~A script that automatically~~[Automated](#) ~~assembles~~[yes](#) from the labelled data a standards-
137 and checklist- compliant draft [SR](#) protocol document ([“automated documentation”](#)).

138 We emphasise that this is a proof-of-concept project. As far as we are aware, a general-
139 purpose operational protocol has not been developed for SRs, nor has automated
140 documentation from data gathered during SR protocol development been demonstrated. As a
141 proof of concept, our technology stack is a prototype and code has not been finessed. [Our](#)
142 ~~target audiences in this paper are~~ [not novice SR authors but other tool developers who are](#)

143 ~~seeking to create tools that can eventually support SR authors in being standards-compliant,~~
144 ~~and people working in research policy who are interested in what such tools might look like and~~
145 ~~how they might be expected to work.~~ While we have endeavoured to create something that
146 could be useful in current form, the general-purpose protocol primarily exists for testing and
147 further development of ideas. We cover various aspects of the limitations and development
148 needs of our approach in the Discussion section, below.

149 **Materials and Methods System Design**

150 **Operational procedure**

151 For the general-purpose protocol we revived an experimental build of a ~~general-purpose~~
152 ~~SR~~~~step-by-step operationalisation of protocol based on~~ the COSTER recommendations ~~for~~
153 ~~conducting environmental health systematic reviews. The general-purpose protocol experimental~~
154 ~~build was~~; created ~~using in~~ the protocols.io bench protocol platform (Whaley, 2020; [protocols.io](#)
155 [accessed 7 July 2022](#)). COSTER is an adaptation for human environmental health SRs of
156 Cochrane's MECIR standard (Whaley, Aiassa, *et al.*, 2020). To build the general-purpose
157 protocol, PW abstracted from COSTER all recommendations relevant to the planning of a SR
158 and interpreted them into a sequence of [41](#) explicit operational steps. The ~~resulting 41~~
159 operational steps include instructions on data that should be collected during each step and the
160 conditions under which each step should be marked as complete (Figure 1).

161 **Compliance mapping**

162 PW ~~then~~ cross-referenced each operational step against data reporting requirements for [the](#)
163 [reporting checklists](#) PRISMA-P (Moher *et al.*, 2015), PRISMA-S (Rethlefsen *et al.*, 2021),
164 ROSES for SR protocols (Haddaway *et al.*, 2018), and PROSPERO registrations (Booth *et al.*,
165 2012), ~~to map how completion of each step contributes to fulfilling the reporting requirements of~~
166 ~~several commonly-used protocol reporting checklists.~~

167 **Data labelling**

168 ~~Finally~~, PW created [a hierarchical schema for labelling the data collected by completing each](#)
169 ~~step of the general-purpose protocol. labels for each operational step, and the data that is~~
170 ~~collected during each step. The results of the cross-referencing and step and data labelling~~
171 ~~processes are shown in~~ [The first-level data labels and cross-walk with existing SR guidance and](#)

172 [reporting checklists is shown in Table 1. The complete labelling schema is available at](#)
 173 <https://osf.io/vw4e3>.

174 [The labelled data is of two types. A run of Each step of the general purpose protocol requires](#)
 175 [prompts a users to input one or both of two types of data](#). For brief, structured data, the user
 176 inputs data into the “smart component” feature of protocols.io (shown in Figure 1). For complex,
 177 unstructured data, such as contextual justification for the SR, the user creates a [separate-MS](#)
 178 [Word](#) document, gives the document a specific name as per protocol instructions, and adds it to
 179 an OSF archive. (This is a workaround for limits on data entry in the [current-version](#) of
 180 protocols.io [we were using for the project](#).) Instructions for creating an archive, naming the
 181 documents, and a link to an OSF template archive with pre-named template documents are
 182 included in the general protocol. ~~We created a script to parse the results of a protocol run and~~
 183 ~~the content of the OSF archive, and stitch the data together for automating the creation of draft~~
 184 ~~protocol documentation.~~

Figure 1. Operationalisation into the general protocol of COSTER Recommendation 1.1.2: “Identify information management practices for each stage of the review, including reference and knowledge management tools, systematic review software, and statistics packages.”

185 [Automation of protocolled documentation](#)

186 [The process of following all the steps of the general-purpose protocol through to completion](#)
 187 [is called in protocols.io a “run”. A record of a protocol-run creates of our general-purpose](#)

188 [protocols](#) consists of the following data: the instance of the run in protocols.io itself, that can be
 189 exported as a JSON document; the data entered into the smart components, that is included in
 190 the protocols.io JSON export (the structured data); and the collection of documents uploaded to
 191 the OSF record created by the user during the run (the unstructured data). To automatically
 192 convert this the run data into a draft protocol document, we created a two step-process as
 193 shown in (Figure 2).

194 ~~We created a script to parse the results of a protocol run and the content of the OSF archive,
 195 and stitch the data together for automating the creation of draft protocol documentation. We
 196 created a tool that extracts structured data from both protocols.io and the associated OSF
 197 records, cross-references these against existing SR reporting standards, and integrates the
 198 resulting data into reports according to a given template. In this project we only had capacity to
 199 develop one template, that is a complete report of the protocol planning process. However, third
 200 parties will be able to use our code and labelling to develop additional templates. The
 201 automated documentation process has two stages, as shown in Figure 2.~~

202 **Figure 2.** The process for automating the documentation of a protocol run. Arrows in blue represent interfaces secured using the OAuth2 authentication standard (<https://oauth.net/2/>).

203 The first stage of the process is retrieval. Here, the [completed protocol \(termed a “run” in](#)
 204 [protocols.io\)run](#) is retrieved from protocols.io using their API
 205 (<https://www.protocols.io/developers>). Arrows in blue [in Figure 2](#) represent interfaces secured
 206 using the OAuth2 authentication standard (<https://oauth.net/2/>). The current build of Protocols.io
 207 (accessed 7 July 2022) returns a JSON document that consists of both data entered by the
 208 researcher, and other data including formatting instructions for online display. We therefore had
 209 to write code to extract individual fields from the protocol run via reference to structural features
 210 of the text (e.g. specific punctuation and text block positions). The fields are assigned keys in a
 211 key-value store based on the referenced standards to which they apply and the labels assigned
 212 to the step using square brackets. For example, the entry "Endnote 20" [above for reference](#)

213 [manager](#) would be stored under the key "info_manage" (label). For the entries that contain
214 references to documents stored on the OSF archive created during the protocol run, we retrieve
215 the OSF record using their API (<https://developer.osf.io/>). This yields a set of documents in
216 Microsoft Word .docx format that correspond to stages mentioned in the protocol run. We export
217 the index to JSON and store the documents separately on disk for later use. A sample of our
218 JSON export is shown in Figure 3.

```
{
  "osf_record": "https://osf.io/zjev",
  "comp_infosci": "PW",
  "comp_eviapp": "PW, AB",
  "comp_stats": "SW, EF",
  "comp_topic": "AB, CD",
  "comp_srmeth": "PW",
  "comp_guarant": "PW",
  "info_refman": "ZoteroEndnote 20",
  "info_knowman": "DistillerSR",
  "info_srsoft": "DistillerSR",
  "info_statspack": "R",
  "info_aitools": "Active Screener",
  "fund_sources": "SR Funder 100",
  "fund_funders": "Funded by general grant",
  "fund_grantnum": "12345",
  "fund_fundrole": "None",
  "interests": "https://osf.io/ejcyw",
  "need": "https://osf.io/vp7ak",
  "q_pop_species": "Human",
  "q_pop_sex": "Male",
  "q_pop_age": "45-65",
  "q_pop_health": "Healthy",
  "q_pop_add": "None",
  "q_exp_exp": "Phthalates",
  "q_exp_timing": "Before birth",
  "q_exp_dur": "Any",
  "q_exp_dose": "Any",
  "q_exp_add": "None",
  "q_comp_exp": "Lower levels of phthalate exposure",
  "q_comp_timing": "Before birth",
  "q_comp_dur": "Any",
  "q_comp_dose": "Lower",
  "q_comp_add": "Exclude studies with simulataneous exposure to
pesticides",
  "q_out_primary": "Gout",
  "q_out_second": "Kidney disease",
  [truncated]
}
```

219 **Figure 3:** A truncated sample of structured data in JSON format, as extracted from the protocol run.

220 The second stage of the automated documentation [system-process](#) takes these data as input
 221 and reassembles them according to a template (an example template can be found at
 222 <https://osf.io/nckwu>). This supports two templating languages. The first is a simple subset of
 223 “mustache” markup, a widely-used templating language (<https://mustache.github.io/>). Here,
 224 entries from the JSON document representing structured data from the protocols.io run can be
 225 inserted into free text. For example, the entry “{{info_refman}}” is resolved to “Endnote 20”, as
 226 per the example in Figure 3. The second, an unnamed proprietary template language, allows
 227 template authors to include the contents of an external .docx file completely within the target
 228 document, allowing them to concatenate OSF records in any order. The output of this
 229 templating process is a Microsoft Word document. In our case, this is a complete summary of all
 230 data from the run, intended to be edited by the reviewer into a SR protocol manuscript;
 231 however, templates for [summarising run data into a PRISMA report](#) ~~ts~~ [and/or](#) other structured
 232 documents could also be created.

233 **Table 1.** Cross-walk of the top-level data labels and steps of the general-purpose protocol with items in the conduct
 234 standards and reporting checklists with which the protocol is designed to facilitate compliance. For a complete list of
 235 labels [and](#) definitions, see <https://osf.io/vw4e3>

Labels	Meaning of Labels	Step of General Protocol	Related Conduct Standard-Guideline or Reporting Checklist Items				
			COSTER	PRISMA-P	PRISMA-S	ROSES	PROSPERO (human SRs)
osf_record	Title and URL of accompanying Open Science Framework record	1	-	1a, 1b	-	1	1
competencies	Key competencies of the SR team	2	1.1.1	3b (partial)	16	-	6, 11
info_manage	Information management practices for the SR	3	1.1.2	11a	-	-	26
funding	Information about funding of the SR	4	-	5a, 5b, 5c	-	-	12

interests	Conflicts of interest management policy	5	1.1.3, 1.1.4	-	-	38	13
need	Explanation of need for the SR	6	1.2.1	6	-	5	-
rationale	The theoretical framework that supports the choice of question and use of SR methods to answer it.	7	1.2.2	6	-	5	-
question	The question being answered by the SR, characterised as a PECO statement	8	1.2.3	7, 12, 13	-	7, 8	15, 24, 25
eligibility	The eligibility criteria for evidence to be included in the SR	9	1.3	8	-	20	18-23
screening	The approach to screening evidence for eligibility for the SR	10	3.1	11b	-	18-20	26
multi_publications	The strategy for handling multiple publications from the same eligible study	11	3.4	-	-	-	-
search	The search strategy for the SR	12	1.4.1, 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 2.6	9, 10	1-6, 8, 10, 11	9, 10, 15	16, 17
rerun_search	The plans for re-running the search	13	2.7	-	12	17	16
rob	The risk of bias assessment	14	1.4.3, 5.3, section 5	14	-	22, 23	27

	methods for the SR						
other_appr	Other evidence appraisal methods to be used	15	7.8	-	-	22	-
char_incl	The planned characteristics of included studies table	16	1.4.2	-	-	-	-
extract_forms	The forms to be used for data extraction	17	1.4.7	12	-	-	-
synth	The methods to be used for synthesising the included evidence	18	1.4.4	15-16	-	30-34	28, 29
certainty	The methods to be used for assessing certainty in the results of the synthesis	19	1.4.5	17	-	23, 35,	-
integration	The methods to be used for integrating multiple streams of evidence	20	1.4.6	-	-	-	-
pilot_screening	Instruction to pilot the screening methods	21	1.4.7				
pilot_extraction	Instruction to pilot the data extraction forms	22	1.4.7	11c	-	25, 26	-
pilot_robot	Instruction to pilot the risk of bias assessment methods	23	1.4.7	-	-	-	-
pilot_certainty	Instruction to pilot the certainty	24	1.4.7	-	-	-	-

	assessment methods						
write	Instruction to create a draft protocol document from the above steps	25	-	-	-	-	-
registration	Instructions and location data for registration of the protocol document	26	1.5.1	2	-	-	-
peer_review	Instructions for peer-review of the protocol document	27	1.5.2	-	14	-	-
publication	Instructions and location data for publication of the peer-reviewed protocol document	28	1.5.3	-	-	-	34
Items not covered in general template		PRISMA-P		Not covered: 2, 3a, 3b, 4. 12 is covered by rationale (protocol step 7)			
		PRISMA-S		Not covered: 7, 16. 9 is covered by eligibility criteria. 13, 15 not relevant for a protocol			
		ROSES		Not covered: 2, 3, 4, 6, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 21, 27, 29, 36, 37. 16 (search validation) should be added in a future update. 19, 22, 28: COSTER recommends duplicate screening and appraisal so consistency checking is implicitly covered			
		PROSPERO		Not covered: 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8, 9, 10, 14, 30, 31, 32, 33, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40. Mainly administrative data for PROSPERO			

236

237 Expected Anticipated results of rRunning pProtocol

238 The general-purpose protocol is available at

239 <https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.n92ldydzxl5b/v3>. A run of the general-purpose protocol

240 is anticipated to yields three primary outputs:

- 241 1. A comprehensive record of key data that is needed for [auditing-evaluating the extent to](#)
242 [which a SR protocol is compliant with five important guidance and reporting checklists.](#)
243 [This data is standards-compliance and/or writing up the planning process of a systematic](#)
244 [review,](#) generated ~~in the process of~~ [while the user recording the completion of](#) ~~completes~~
245 each step of the operationalised general protocol, [rather than retrospectively after a](#)
246 [protocol development process has been completed.](#)
- 247 2. Labelled SR protocol data that, [using templates,](#) can [in principle](#) be reassembled into
248 any protocol documentation format, e.g. a conference abstract, PROSPERO registration,
249 a protocol manuscript, a PRISMA report, a response to a data sharing request, etc.
- 250 3. After running the TARPd code, a draft SR protocol manuscript. ~~As a~~ [Because the](#) draft
251 [manuscript is generated by merging that merges labelled data](#) into a fixed template,
252 significant editing will be required [before it could be considered publishable,](#) ~~but~~
253 [However, since the all](#) necessary information is approximately correctly located under
254 relevant subheadings, [all required information is present and can be rearranged, with no](#)
255 [information omitted.](#)

256 An example run consisting of a PDF showing what data was input during a test run of the
257 general-purpose protocol, the processed JSON output from the test run, and an automatically
258 generated .docx template created from the test run, are available at <https://osf.io/m35px/>
259 (“Protocol publication” section). Code for the JSON conversion and .docx document generation
260 is available at <https://github.com/StephenWattam/TARPd>.

261 Discussion

262 *Comparison to similar tools*

263 We did not do a systematic review of existing tools for this project, but we did search for
264 similar initiatives from a number of sources. PW screened all GitHub records tagged as
265 “systematic-review”, “systematic-reviews”, or “systematic-literature-reviews”, the first 10 pages
266 of results of a Google search for “automated reporting of systematic reviews”, the first 100
267 results sorted by relevance for searching “systematic review” on the protocols.io platform, the
268 protocol and reporting tools indexed in the Systematic Review Toolbox
269 (<http://systematicreviewtools.com/>), and the SR support tools reviewed by Kohl et al. (2018).
270 PW also followed up on word-of-mouth recommendations received from discussion of this

271 project with [our peers/colleagues](#). For any tool that looked potentially similar to the present
272 project, PW checked public documentation of tool features for information about its functionality.
273 Given the limited documentation that often accompanies tools, we note that our descriptions of
274 a tool may not be a true reflection of the tool's actual feature set.

275 The majority of GitHub records seemed to consist of document classifiers designed to
276 support the screening of search results for a SR, along with some tools to support the
277 development of search strategies. We did not find anything obviously related to facilitating
278 [standard-compliance with guidance](#) or [reporting](#) checklists ~~compliance~~. While protocols.io has
279 been used as a repository for SR protocols, no SRs appear to have been constructed as
280 operational procedures in the platform. Methods-Wizard from the SR-Accelerator (Clark *et al.*,
281 2020) does have features that generate methods text from input data, but it does not seem to
282 generate labelled data that is designed to be machine-readable, and it does not obviously
283 operationalise the step-by-step process of developing a SR protocol. We did note the existence
284 of a tool for reporting trials in behavioural sciences, the Paper Authoring Tool (West, 2020), that
285 generates labelled data, has features for automated drafting of a manuscript, and covers some
286 aspects of standards compliance (although without explicit cross-walking). It was not clear if the
287 Paper Authoring Tool is intended to be completed retrospectively, or is a tool that also
288 operationalises the process of planning a study in a way that facilitates compliance with conduct
289 standards.

290 Cochrane's RevMan software for conducting SRs of health research (Cochrane, 2020)
291 appears to be the closest relative of our general-purpose protocol (desktop version 5.4.1,
292 released 21 September 2020). RevMan connects components of a SR protocol or final report to
293 the individual requirements of the MECIR standards, which in turn direct authors to detailed
294 methodological guidance in the relevant sections of the Cochrane Handbook. However,
295 RevMan is a reporting-focused tool that leaves implicit the step-by-step procedures one would
296 follow as a researcher that would result in compliance with MECIR. For example, RevMan does
297 not as an explicit step ask a research team to designate a librarian or information specialist as
298 part of an operational process that increases the effectiveness of search strategies for a review.
299 Also, while some aspects of reporting are automated by the simple provision in RevMan of a
300 structured template designed around PRISMA compliance, authors still manually enter
301 information [retrospectively](#) based on their own separate documentation of their process, rather
302 than the SR report being directly generated from ~~that~~ data [immediately](#) recorded ~~during~~ each
303 operational step. Finally, RevMan is optimised for one SR reporting task (completing a

304 Cochrane review) rather than designed to generate labelled data that can easily be repurposed
305 for any SR reporting task.

306 Overall, we did not identify a tool that does all three tasks of interpreting a SR protocol into a
307 series of operational steps linked explicitly to SR conduct standards and reporting checklists,
308 collecting structured labelled data in completing those steps, and then automatically generating
309 draft documentation using that data.

310 *Potential strengths of our approach*

311 We believe our approach to a general-purpose SR protocol has three interrelated potential
312 advantages that can be further explored and developed. These are: an emphasis on [templated,](#)
313 algorithmic [approaches to conducting and reporting research](#) rather than heuristic approaches
314 ~~to conducting and reporting research~~; taking a view of conduct standards and reporting
315 checklists as being analogous to open-source software; and the positioning of labelled data
316 rather than a study manuscript as the primary output of the research process. We discuss these
317 briefly below.

318 *Algorithmic over heuristic approaches to conducting research*

319 Algorithms are a method for solving a problem in a finite number of steps via the application
320 of a set of formally-defined processes or rules. Heuristics are practical methods for problem-
321 solving that are derived from previous experiences with similar problems. Our opinion is that
322 systematic review is a [study](#) design ~~of study~~ that tends to be conducted heuristically, but could
323 be made more accessible to researchers if formalised to be more algorithmic. Our general-
324 purpose protocol is an attempt to do this.

325 We note that our approach is algorithmic more in the sense of a detailed recipe in a cook-
326 book than in the more formal sense of being computable. A recipe formalises a sequence of
327 inputs (ingredients) and steps that need to be followed in order to generate an output (a
328 chocolate drip cake). The purpose of the recipe is to transfer expertise between cooks without
329 them having to physically meet, one to directly train another, or a cook having to intuit the recipe
330 from the ingredients and whatever cake-making experience they may have previously acquired.
331 Successfully following the recipe still requires experience and experimentation, but the purpose
332 of the recipe is to reduce that requirement: it means cooks don't have to remember or

333 internalise a full set of complex rules, making the possibility of successfully creating the final
334 dish more accessible.

335 Algorithmic protocols could similarly help with standard and checklist compliance. In codifying
336 a set of recommended practices and the recording of data outputs from following them,
337 compliance can become a [byproduct-by-product](#) of following the algorithm rather than something
338 additional that a researcher has to factor into the conduct and documentation of a study. This
339 may help address the problem of consistent under-reporting of key methodological information
340 in SR protocol registrations (Booth *et al.*, 2020) and, if extended beyond SR, also for primary
341 studies (Macleod *et al.*, 2021).

342 [Standards-Guidance and checklists](#) as open-source software

343 Our approach makes it more transparent how the recommendations and requirements of one
344 or more conduct [standardsguidelines](#), or the requirements that are implicit in one or more
345 reporting checklists, have been interpreted into an operational procedure. Unlike static
346 documents such as the PRISMA checklist (Page *et al.*, 2021), we built our procedure in a
347 platform that emulates some aspects of software development. Protocols.io implements several
348 GitHub-like collaboration features (<https://github.com/>) that allow users of the general protocol to
349 independently build on and develop our prototype. These include allowing users to post
350 questions and comments on each step of the protocol (Figure 4), and to fork protocols for
351 independent development. Forking is particularly important for tracking versions of protocols.

352 Once an operational procedure has been written up and shared, it can be discussed, tested,
353 and finessed by those who are using it. Returning to our recipe analogy, cooks will modify
354 recipes for working in environments where an ingredient may need to be substituted for dietary
355 requirements, lack of availability, or for different tastes. Processes may be adapted for different
356 circumstances or levels of skill that may make some culinary techniques unrealistic to
357 implement. This is authoring, adapting, and versioning of the algorithm according to need.

358 Presenting the variations on a platform where relationships between versions are tracked
 359 helps make adaptations discoverable and evaluable, and allows the evolution of processes to
 360 be observed. It also implies an approach to standardisation that is more bottom-up and [directly](#)
 361 responsive to ~~the community~~ needs [of the user community](#) than the approaches traditionally
 362 recommended for developing standards and checklists, such as the review-workshop-document
 363 process of Moher et al. (2014). We anticipate this resulting in clouds of related micro-standards
 364 adapted around the specific needs of individual research communities. While this might sound
 365 chaotic to some, forking and versioning may allow adaptations of standards to be more
 366 transparent than the often unclear ways in which users currently interpret compliance with e.g.
 367 the PRISMA checklist.

The screenshot shows a protocol step titled "D. Defining the strategy for searching for evidence relevant to the review objectives". The step is numbered 12 and contains the following text: "[search] **Design sufficiently sensitive search strategies**, so that studies which meet the eligibility criteria of the review are not inadvertently excluded. Document the search methods in sufficient detail to render them transparent and reproducible. *COSTER 1.4.1, 2.6 / PROSPERO 17 / PRISMA-P 9, 10*". Below this are three numbered sub-steps: 1. Create a .docx format document named "LiteratureSearch" (or use the template provided at <https://osf.io/2ysk3>); 2. Complete each of the sub-steps below; 3. Upload the complete document to the OSF record. At the bottom, it says "Mark this step as **complete** when all relevant sub-steps are complete and the LiteratureSearch document has been uploaded to the OSF Record." To the right of the step is a comment box with a search bar, a plus icon, and a comment from Paul Whaley dated Jul 26, 2022. The comment reads: "A step relating to validation of the search strategy should be added, for compliance with ROSES item 16." Below the comment is a "REPLY" button.

368 **Figure 4:** An example of how a user can comment on a step of the protocol to suggest a feature or improvement. A
 369 user could also generate a fork of the protocol to add steps specific to their own requirements.

370 *Labelled data as primary, manuscripts as derivative*

371 Our approach positions labelled data as the primary output of the process of conducting a
 372 research activity, with documentation as a secondary output that is derived from labelled data.
 373 This reconfigures the conventional flow of data reuse in research, whereby [researchers](#)
 374 [generate data, describe the methods for acquiring and how they interpret their data in largely](#)
 375 [unstructured form via a published document, data is generated, a document describing the](#)
 376 [acquisition and interpretation of data is published, and from which then other](#) researchers have
 377 to abstract ~~from that document~~ the data they need for reproducing or extending the original
 378 study.

379 When data, including data about methods, is labelled, compliance with a reporting checklist
 380 can become a matter of running code that generates a compliant manuscript, rather than
 381 retrospectively (and usually manually) cross-checking a document against a complex but routine
 382 set of reporting requirements. This kind of cross-checking is the sort of detailed but repetitive
 383 task that should be automated. Labelled data is also interoperable: code can be written to
 384 generate reports that are consistently compliant with one or more different reporting checklists.
 385 Availability of such code should reduce the requirement for an author of a SR protocol to be
 386 experienced in any particular reporting format in order for them to produce a comprehensive,
 387 checklist-compliant report (illustrated in Figure 5).

388
 389 **Figure 5:** Illustration of how the general-purpose protocol operationalises conduct standards into practical steps
 390 generating labelled data, which can be assembled into checklist-compliant protocol manuscripts. We believe this flow
 391 should be applicable to any study design, not just SR protocols.

392 ***Current limitations and future development***

393 *Technical issues*

394 The proof-of-concept system described above is limited by a number of technical factors in
395 our technology stack that need to be addressed via changes to the stack and/or development of
396 the components within it.

397 Firstly is the difficulty in processing Microsoft Word documents in Python. Library support for
398 templating, reading, and writing .docx files exists and is mature, but the feature set is limited.
399 We found that existing libraries were not able to apply templates reliably, nor to inspect
400 documents to separately extract text and tables in-order. This limited our templating features to
401 basic inclusion of fields within running text, or concatenation of full documents (for example,
402 documents can only be concatenated by appending them to the end of a manuscript rather than
403 inserting them in the correct place; while they are in the correct order, the user needs to cut and
404 paste to the correct location). It also makes it easy to break our code, as it looks for text features
405 which if in a different place will not be found. Updating our protocol therefore has to be done
406 with care to preserve structure, which carries implicit rules and is therefore more likely to break.

407 Secondly, it is apparent that the format used by protocols.io to deliver data over their API is
408 primarily aimed at displaying such data via a web browser, that is, the content is difficult to
409 separate from its formatting. OSF records exhibit a similar issue: though every object within the
410 OSF system has a unique ID that makes referencing simple in principle, this ID is not exposed
411 to the end user except in certain circumstances, meaning it is difficult for users to link directly to
412 documents when completing a protocol run. This could be solved a number of ways, though
413 within our system we relied on unique filenames to identify entries.

414 Thirdly, data collection features in protocols.io are not yet well-developed. The platform has
415 been designed for recording bench protocols, with data collected mainly for the purpose of
416 process auditing and validation. We appropriated these data collection features for recording
417 data from completion of a step of the general purpose protocol, but with limited success. The
418 number of .docx documents that need to be uploaded to an OSF record is an example of a
419 workaround to address this issue. Allowing users to easily create richer documentation in-situ
420 [within the protocol run](#) would be preferable to creating and linking to a series of documents
421 external to the general protocol template.

422 Mitigating these limitations requires either significant software engineering effort using
423 current technology choices, or changing to a different technology stack. Regarding the latter, we
424 suggest changing the [templating format from Word to format used for templating](#) to HTML,
425 which has a much more mature ecosystem of development tools, and [is relatively](#)
426 [straightforward to later post-processing to](#) convert to .docx formats if and when required. Other
427 languages and platforms (such as .net) may provide better support for editing such formats.

428 *General development*

429 We only did enough development of our general-purpose protocol to prove the concept.
430 ~~There could be additional~~[Further](#) operational steps [could be added](#) to realise a more complete
431 mapping of conduct and reporting requirements, particularly for PROSPERO where
432 administrative data is lacking from our general protocol, and for item 16 of ROSES that asks for
433 information about validation of search strategy ~~which we overlooked~~. Nor has our
434 operationalisation been user-tested or optimised. We also think that modularisation of our
435 protocol would be helpful for improving the efficiency of development and testing, and providing
436 opportunities for finessing specific components of the operationalised process independently on
437 an as-needed basis, as per the open software analogy discussed above. For example, we have
438 previously created a protocol for pilot-testing the screening process of a SR (Whaley, Garside
439 and Eales, 2020), that could be a module for step 21 of our general-purpose protocol.

440 While ~~we have labelled our~~ data [labelling that](#) allows computational assembly of protocol
441 documentation, our tooling does not yet extend to doing anything computational with the data
442 that has been labelled. Introducing and exploiting semantic authoring features for increased
443 machine-readability and more granular labelling that is integrated with ontologies would be
444 beneficial for a number of reasons (Whaley, Edwards, *et al.*, 2020), including interoperability of
445 data between systems and the validation of entered data.

446 We also note that conduct standards and reporting checklists [can be viewed as are](#)
447 interventions ~~that aim to improve~~[for improving](#) research quality via the dissemination of written
448 instructions. We believe we have good theoretical reasons for thinking our approach could be a
449 more effective intervention than conventional standards and checklists, but there is not [yet any](#)
450 empirical evidence that this is the case. Therefore, there should be research into how effective
451 our approach is, for whom it works best, how much the granularity of operationalisation affects
452 effectiveness, among other ideas. In comparison to conventional approaches, our bottom-up
453 approach to standardisation will have its own challenges in relation to development, evaluation,

454 and validation of the standards that are produced, and the creation of suitable workflows for
 455 addressing them in what will be a nebulous and distributed standards ecosystem.

456 Finally, even if the system is shown to be effective among users, there is no guarantee there
 457 will be enough users of the system to make a difference to the general publishing standards
 458 such systems seek to improve. We are encouraged by a recent pilot study that suggests
 459 researchers may be open to increased formalisation of the reporting of study data (Wilkins *et al.*,
 460 2022), and our approach is built on the assumption that automated research documentation will
 461 incentivise use of operationalised protocols. However, we do not have a well-developed theory
 462 based on empirical evidence as to what conditions need to be fulfilled in order for significant
 463 uptake of a system such as [the one](#) we have prototyped. We subscribe to the view that
 464 infrastructure should be viewed broadly as an installed base of both technology and social
 465 arrangements, including group membership and conventions of practice (Edwards *et al.*, 2009),
 466 and that successfully securing uptake of systems analogous to ours will require both to be
 467 addressed.

468 Conclusion

469 We have presented a general-purpose SR protocol that is intended to serve as a proof-of-
 470 concept for improving compliance with SR conduct standards and reporting checklists. [We](#)
 471 [theorised that general-purpose protocols would work, principally](#) by reducing the experience
 472 requirement for successfully using [SRs](#) such standards and checklists in a research process. We
 473 articulated some of the potential advantages of our approach, including viewing the problem of
 474 compliance as benefiting from an algorithm-like solution, treating the development of research
 475 standards and checklists as being analogous to open-source software development, and the
 476 positioning of labelled data as the primary output of research from which a manuscript is a
 477 derivative product. We acknowledge a range of issues with our existing technology stack, and
 478 outline a plan for further development that includes technical development and the generation of
 479 empirical evidence for the effectiveness of our proposed approach.

480 Supporting Information (Data, Code, and Research Materials)

Item	Link
Document templates for complex protocol data that cannot be directly entered into the general-purpose protocol	https://osf.io/h7w68/

List of labels for the protocol data	https://osf.io/vw4e3
Labelled template for generating automated protocol documentation	https://osf.io/nckwu
Draft protocol from test run (test run #7)	https://osf.io/zr78y
JSON database from test run (test run #7)	https://osf.io/63tmz
PDF of data entered into Protocols.io on test run (test run #7)	https://osf.io/t3z98
Full set of documents created for test run and uploaded to OSF as per general-purpose protocol instructions (test run #7)	https://osf.io/m35px/
Code for JSON conversion from Protocols.io protocol run and document generation	https://github.com/StephenWattam/TARPD

481

482 **Metadata**

483 **Funding**

484 Lancaster University Impact Acceleration Award: “TARPD Prototype Tool for Automated
485 Research Project Documentation”

486 **Preregistration**

487 This study was not preregistered.

488 **Declaration of Interests**

489 PW declares the following financial interests: consultancy services for the Evidence-Based
490 Toxicology Collaboration (EBTC) at Johns Hopkins University Bloomberg School of Public
491 Health; Lancaster University, mainly around securing impact of his PhD research (completed
492 2020); the University of Central Lancashire (UCLAN), which has involved developing furniture
493 fire safety models relevant to reducing the impact of the use of chemical flame retardants in
494 ensuring fire safety for the UK Government Agency OPSS; and for Yordas Group, to deliver
495 training in SR methods for EU JRC. PW also receives an Honorarium as Systematic Reviews
496 Editor for the journal Environment International. In general, PW’s consultancy work is around
497 development and promotion of systematic review methods in environmental health research,
498 delivering training around these methods, and providing editorial services. He is applying for
499 funding to develop evidence surveillance and automated SR documentation methods through
500 Lancaster University, which if successful will arrive within the next two years.

501 PW also declares the following non-financial interests: a historical, public commitment to high
502 quality systematic review methods in support of environmental health policy and decision-
503 making; active involvement in a range of projects intended to improve research standards in
504 evidence synthesis. These include development of SR conduct standards (e.g. COSTER),
505 reporting checklists (e.g. ROSES), and critical appraisal tools (e.g. CREST_Triage, IV-CAT) to
506 support the production of high quality systematic reviews, evidence maps, and other study
507 designs. PW is an active member of the GRADE Working Group, has a senior role at EBTC that
508 involves promoting SR and other evidence-based methods in toxicology and environmental
509 health, and is a member of an informal UK NGO network promoting good environmental policy
510 in the UK, and several Brussels-based environmental policy advocacy groups including HEAL

511 and EEB. In general, PW has a strong interest in supporting precautionary, evidence-based
512 approaches to environmental health policy.

513 SW declares providing scientific & technical consultancy services as a subcontractor to PW
514 on a UK OPSS-funded study into the use of chemical fire retardants in furniture. SW has also
515 provided scientific consultancy services in unrelated fields, and states that publication of work in
516 any area impacts chances of future employment.

517 AMS declares that, as part of her role at Bond University, she provides training in: evidence-
518 based medicine and systematic review methodology (including automation tools), to Australia-
519 based academics, clinicians and students. Those workshops charge a registration fee. AMS is
520 part of the Systematic Review Accelerator team at Bond University, which develops and makes
521 publicly available automation tools to accelerate completion of systematic reviews, as well as
522 conducting research in this area (all tools are available free of charge). ~~From October 2022,~~
523 AMS ~~will be~~is an Associate Editor for Systematic Reviews, a BMC / Springer Nature journal
524 (non-remunerated).

525 JV is a Senior Research Associate at Lancaster University and declares having no interests
526 that may compromise the integrity of the research described in this manuscript.

527 **Ethics Declarations**

528 Ethical approval and informed consent were not required for this research, as it involved neither
529 human nor animal participants.

530 **Data availability**

531 All data is available from the accompanying OSF project record at
532 <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/ZJEVP> and GitHub repository at
533 <https://github.com/StephenWattam/TARPD>

534 **Authors' Contributions**

535 *Created using Tenzing app (Holcombe et al., 2020).*

536 Conceptualization: Paul Whaley. Data curation: Stephen Wattam. Funding acquisition: Paul
537 Whaley and John Vidler. Investigation: Paul Whaley and Stephen Wattam. Methodology: Paul
538 Whaley and Stephen Wattam. Project administration: John Vidler. Software: Stephen Wattam.
539 Supervision: John Vidler. Validation: Stephen Wattam. Visualisation: Paul Whaley and Stephen

540 Wattam. Writing - original draft: Paul Whaley. Writing - review & editing: Paul Whaley, Stephen
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